

RECOMBINANT PLASMID pET-28A(+)-ThPNP ENCODING *THERMUS THERMOPHILUS* PURINE NUCLEOSIDE PHOSPHORYLASE

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18845045>

Abstract. Purine nucleoside phosphorylase (PNP) catalyzes the reversible phosphorolysis of purine nucleosides and is widely used as a biocatalyst for the synthesis of nucleoside analogues. Thermophilic PNPs are of particular interest due to their enhanced stability and activity at elevated temperatures. In this study, a recombinant plasmid, pET-28a(+)-ThPNP (6058 bp), carrying the 716 bp purine nucleoside phosphorylase gene from *Thermus thermophilus*, was constructed for heterologous expression in *Escherichia coli*. The developed construct provides a basis for efficient production of recombinant enzyme and supports further applications in enzymatic synthesis of pharmaceutically relevant modified nucleosides.

Keywords: modified nucleosides, nucleoside phosphorylases, PNP, *Thermus thermophilus*.

Introduction

Nucleoside phosphorylases (NPs) are versatile enzymes widely used for the synthesis of modified nucleosides with potential therapeutic applications in oncology as well as antiviral and antibacterial therapy [1-3]. Based on substrate specificity, these enzymes are classified into purine nucleoside phosphorylases (PNP, EC 2.4.2.1) and pyrimidine nucleoside phosphorylases (PyNP, EC 2.4.2.2). Both groups play a central role in the nucleotide salvage pathway by catalyzing the reversible phosphorolysis of nucleosides, thereby maintaining intracellular nucleotide homeostasis [4-6]. Enzymatic approaches offer significant advantages over conventional chemical synthesis, including improved regioselectivity and greater control of trans glycosylation reactions, making them efficient tools for the production of nucleoside analogues [7-12]. Thermophilic enzymes, such as *Thermus thermophilus* PNP, exhibit enhanced structural stability at elevated temperatures and therefore represent promising candidates for industrial biocatalysis [13-18]. Recombinant expression in *Escherichia coli* enables the production of sufficient quantities of enzyme for detailed investigations of catalytic efficiency, substrate specificity, and protein engineering. Such studies help bridge fundamental biochemical knowledge with practical applications in enzyme-based synthesis and therapeutic development.

The aim of this study was to construct a plasmid DNA encoding recombinant purine nucleoside phosphorylase from *Thermus thermophilus* and to express it in *Escherichia coli* cells in order to obtain a high-yield enzyme producer suitable for biotechnological applications.

Materials and methods. Transfer vector pET-28a(+) was purchased from Novagen (Cat. 69864-3). Restriction enzymes *EcoRI* and *NotI*, as well as T4 DNA ligase, were obtained from Thermo Scientific. All other chemicals were of the highest analytical grade and purchased from Sigma-Aldrich. The recombinant plasmid pPICZ α A-ThPNP, deposited in the Laboratory of Molecular Genetics ICPS Ruz, was used as the template for amplification of the purine nucleoside phosphorylase gene.

Preparation of transfer vector pET-28a (+) and cDNA (gene) of ThPNP

One microgram of the transfer vector pET-28a(+) was sequentially digested with the restriction endonucleases *EcoRI* and *NotI*. The linearized DNA fragment (5350 bp) was separated by electrophoresis in 0.7% agarose gel and purified using the PureLink™ Quick Gel Extraction Kit (Thermo Scientific) [19].

The *Thermus thermophilus* purine nucleoside phosphorylase cDNA (deoD gene insert, 716 bp) was amplified by PCR using the recombinant plasmid pPICZαA-PNP as a template and the following primers:

Forward: 5'-GACTGGTTCCAATTGACAAGC-3'

Reverse: 5'-GCAAATGGCATTCTGACATCC-3'

After electrophoresis in 1% agarose gel, the PCR product was excised and purified using the same gel extraction kit and subsequently digested with *EcoRI* and *NotI*, identical to the enzymes used for preparation of the transfer vector.

Ligation of the vector with cDNA (ThPNP gene).

Ligation of the pET-28a(+) vector with the *Thermus thermophilus* purine nucleoside phosphorylase gene (ThPNP) was performed in a total reaction volume of 10 μL at a vector-to-insert molar ratio of 1:4 using recombinant bacteriophage T4 DNA ligase (Thermo Scientific) (Fig. 1) [20].

Transformation of E. coli TOP10 with the ligation mixture.

Following ligation, DNA was precipitated, and the resulting pellet was dissolved in 10 μL of deionized water. The dissolved recombinant DNA was introduced into electrocompetent plasmid-free *Escherichia coli TOP10* cells (Invitrogen) by electroporation according to the established protocol [20].

Identification of recombinant clones containing pET-28a(+)-ThPNP.

Plasmid DNA isolated from transformant clones was analyzed by electrophoresis in 0.8% agarose gel to estimate molecular size. Clones containing plasmid DNA of approximately 6058 bp (pET-28a(+) vector plus deoD insert) were further confirmed by PCR analysis. PCR products were evaluated by electrophoresis in 1% agarose gel [20].

Transformation of pET-28a(+)-ThPNP into E. coli BL21(DE3).

The recombinant pET-28a(+)-ThPNP plasmid was purified and concentrated by ethanol precipitation in the presence of 3 M sodium acetate (pH 5.2). The purified DNA was transformed into *E. coli BL21*(DE3) cells using an Electroporator 2510 (Eppendorf). Transformants were selected on YPD medium supplemented with kanamycin (100 μg/mL) and cultured for subsequent expression studies.

Results and Discussion. This study describes the design and cloning of the recombinant plasmid pET-28a(+)-ThPNP intended for expression of *Thermus thermophilus* purine nucleoside phosphorylase (ThPNP). Purine nucleoside phosphorylase (PNP) catalyzes the reversible phosphorolysis of the glycosidic bond of pentofuranosides in the presence of inorganic phosphate, playing a key role in the nucleotide salvage pathway.

At present, *Escherichia coli* remains one of the most efficient hosts for large-scale production of heterologous recombinant proteins. Therefore, the successful construction of the recombinant plasmid pET-28a(+)-ThPNP represents an important step toward obtaining the target enzyme in *E. coli BL21*(DE3) expression cells.

The recombinant plasmid pET-28a(+)-ThPNP (6058 bp) was generated on the basis of the transfer vector pET-28a(+) (approximately 5340 bp), which is optimized for intracellular protein expression in *E. coli*. The structural elements of the constructed plasmid are illustrated in Fig. 1.

Fig. 1. Physical map of the cloned plasmid DNA pET-28a (+) -ThPNP (6058 bp).

Ligation of the vector with the ThPNP cDNA and subsequent transformation into *E. coli* TOP10 cells were performed as outlined in Fig. 2.

Fig. 2. The general scheme of cloning recombinant plasmid pET-28a(+)-ThPNP

Selection of recombinant clones was carried out on kanamycin-containing medium [23]. Transformants harboring the recombinant plasmid were screened by PCR and restriction analysis,

both of which confirmed the presence of the deoD (ThPNP) insert. PCR analysis of selected clones revealed a DNA fragment of approximately 728 bp (Fig. 3), corresponding to the expected size of the ThPNP gene fragment.

Fig. 3. PCR analysis of transformants. A- DNA Marker; B- Clone containing recombinant pET-28a(+)-ThPNP;

Comparative restriction analysis of the recombinant plasmid pET-28a (+) -ThPNP and the parental vector pET-28a(+) using *EcoRI* is shown in Fig. 4. Electrophoresis in 1% agarose gel produced linear DNA fragments consistent with theoretical sizes derived from plasmid maps. The difference in fragment length between the recombinant and parental plasmids further confirmed successful insertion of the ThPNP gene.

Fig. 4. Restriction of the recombinant plasmid pET-28a(+)-ThPNP and transfer vector by identical restriction site. A. pET-28a(+)-ThPNP (6058 bp); B. pET-28a(+) (5342 bp); (C) DNA Marker.

Conclusion. A novel recombinant plasmid, pET-28a(+)-ThPNP, was successfully constructed for expression of *Thermus thermophilus* purine nucleoside phosphorylase in *E. coli* BL21(DE3) cells. The developed construct enables efficient production of recombinant PNP and may serve as a platform for cost-effective and large-scale enzymatic synthesis of modified nucleosides with potential pharmaceutical applications.

REFERENCES

1. Berdis A. Nucleobase-modified nucleosides and nucleotides: Applications in biochemistry, synthetic biology, and drug discovery. *Front. Chem.* 2022, 10, 1051525. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fchem.2022.1051525>.
2. Gonçalves B.C., Lopes Barbosa M.G., Silva Olak A.P., Belebecha Terezo N., Nishi L., Watanabe M.A., Marinello P., Zendrini Rechenchoski D., Dejato Rocha S.P., Faccin-Galhardi L.C. Antiviral therapies: advances and perspectives. *Fundam. Clin. Pharmacol.* 2021, 35, 305-320. <https://doi.org/10.1111/fcp.12609>
3. Duffy S. et al. Modified nucleic acids: replication, evolution, and next-generation therapeutics. *BMC Biol.* 2020, 18, 112. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12915-020-00803-6>
4. Fernández-Lucas, J.; Camarasa Rius, M.-J. (Eds.) *Enzymatic and Chemical Synthesis of Nucleic Acid Derivatives*; Wiley-VCH: Weinheim, Germany, 2019; ISBN 978-3-527-34376-8.
5. Bzowska A., Kulikowska E., Shugar D. Purine nucleoside phosphorylases: Properties, functions, and clinical aspects // *Pharmacol. Ther.* 2000, 88(3), 349-425 [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0163-7258\(00\)00097-8](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0163-7258(00)00097-8).
6. Kamel, S.; Yehia, H.; Neubauer, P.; Wagner, A. *Enzym Chem Synth Nucleic Acid Deriv.* In Wiley-VCH; Weinheim, Germany, 2018; pp. 1-28. <https://doi.org/10.1002/9783527812103.ch1>.
7. Fateev I.V. Sasmakov S.A. Abdurakhmanov J.M. Ziyaev A.A. et al. Synthesis of substituted 1,2,4-Triazole-3-thione nucleosides using *E. coli* purine nucleoside Phosphorylase. *Biomolecules*, 2024, 14, 745. <https://doi.org/10.3390/biom14070745>
8. Rabuffetti, M.; Bavaro, T.; Semproli, R.; Cattaneo, G.; Massone, M.; Morelli, C.F.; Speranza, G.; Ubiali, D. Synthesis of Ribavirin, Tecadenoson, and Cladribine by Enzymatic Transglycosylation. *Catalysts* 2019, 9, 355. <https://doi.org/10.3390/catal9040355>
9. Fernández-Lucas, J.; Fresco-Taboada, A.; Acebal, C.; de la Mata, I.; Arroyo, M. Enzymatic synthesis of nucleoside analogues using immobilized 2'-deoxyribosyltransferase from *Lactobacillus reuteri*. *Appl. Microbiol. Biotechnol.* 2011, 91, 317-327.
10. Fernández-Lucas, J. Multienzymatic synthesis of nucleic acid derivatives: A general perspective. *Appl. Microbiol. Biotechnol.* 2015, 99, 4615-4627.
11. Mikhailopulo I.A., Miroshnikov A.I. New Trends in Nucleoside Biotechnology. *Acta Nat.* 2010, 2, 36-58.
12. Laponi M.J., Rivero C.W., Zinni M.A., Britos C.N., Trelles J.A. New developments in nucleoside analogues biosynthesis: A review. *J. Mol. Catal. B Enzym.* 2016, 133, 218-233.
13. Fateev I.V., Kostromina M.A., Abramchik Y.A., Eletskaia B.Z., Mikheeva R. et al. Multi-Enzymatic Cascades in the Synthesis of Modified Nucleosides: Comparison of the Thermophilic and Mesophilic Pathways. *Biomolecules* 2021, 11, 586. <https://doi.org/10.3390/biom11040586>

14. Del Arco J., Fernández-Lucas J. Purine and pyrimidine salvage pathway in thermophiles: A valuable source of biocatalysts for the industrial production of nucleic acid derivatives. *Appl. Microbiol. Biotechnol.* 2018, 102, 7805-7820. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00253-018-9242-8>.
15. Szeker K., Zhou X., Schwab T. et al. Comparative Investigations on Thermostable Pyrimidine Nucleoside Phosphorylases from *Geobacillus thermoglucosidasius* and *Thermus thermophilus*. *J. Mol. Catal. B Enzym.* 2012, 84, 27-34.
16. Almendros M., Sinisterra J.V., Berenguer J. *Thermus thermophilus* Strains Active in Purine Nucleoside Synthesis. *Molecules* 2009, 14, 1279-1287.
17. Tomoike F., Kuramitsu S., Masui R. Unique Substrate Specificity of Purine Nucleoside Phosphorylases from *Thermus thermophilus*. *Extremophiles* 2013, 17, 505-514.
18. Almendros M., Berenguer J., Sinisterra J.V. *Thermus thermophilus* nucleoside phosphorylases active in the synthesis of nucleoside analogues. *Appl Environ Microbiol.* 2012, 78(9), 3128-35. <https://doi.org/10.1128/aem.07605-11>
19. Molecular cloning // Pure Link™ Quick Gel Extraction Kit. Catalog number: K210012 - 2022. <https://www.thermofisher.com/order/catalog/product/K210012>
20. Green M.R., Sambrook J. *Molecular cloning. A laboratory manual.* Fourth edition. New York: Cold Spring Harbor Laboratory Press; 2012.